

Wire-arc directed energy deposition of AZ61 magnesium alloy fabricated by cold metal transfer: Processing, microstructure, and mechanical properties

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KEYWORDS: Magnesium alloy, processing, mechanical properties, CMT, WADED, WAAM, AZ61

ABSTRACT

This research examines the limitations of Cold Metal Transfer (CMT) for Wire-Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM – also known as WADED – Wire-arc Directed Energy Deposition) of AZ61 magnesium alloys. Despite the excellent properties of magnesium alloys, their production is challenging due to high vapour pressure, low boiling point, flammability and the complexities of maintaining stable welding processes. This study investigates the effects of crucial CMT parameters, such as boost phase current and duration, burn phase current, electrode speed, and short-circuit (SC) phase current. Key findings highlight the significant effects of boost phase current, cycle time duration, droplet surface tension, and material consumption, which lead to weld size and shape changes. Electrode speed and SC phase current notably influence the stability of the welding process and weld depth. By optimizing these parameters, a stable and efficient welding process that enhanced penetration depth, ideal contact angle, and consistent weld depth, proving beneficial for WADED of magnesium alloys, was achieved. The optimized parameters facilitated the fabrication of a 50-layer thin-walled component, underscoring the study's contribution to advancing CMT applications in WADED processes.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Additive Manufacturing (AM) technology, which utilises layer-upon-layer 3D model data to create objects, provides another promising avenue for manufacturing complex structures. Of the AM techniques, Wire-arc Directed Energy Deposition (WADED) stands out due to its high deposition rate, low material cost, good structural integrity, and time efficiency [1]. This technology, which uses welding wire as the filler metal and welding arc as the heat source, is increasingly used to fabricate large-scale components, a requirement in sectors prioritising lightweight [2, 3].

Among the several welding methods available, gas metal arc welding (GMAW), a high-efficiency filler wire welding method, offers superior gap bridging and compensation for the loss of alloy elements during welding [4]. However, controlling heat input is critical to mitigating complications such as overheated droplets, grain coarsening, oxidation and evaporation, thermal stress, and hot cracking during welding [5]. Hence, Cold Metal Transfer (CMT), a modified GMAW process where the wire is retracted after the short circuit is formed, emerged as a valuable solution [6]. CMT, which reduces heat input and spatter, has shown promising results for the cladding and welding magnesium alloys by mitigating many issues like droplet explosion and thermal stress [7].

Magnesium alloys are characterised by their high strength, low density, excellent castability, high thermal conductivity, and good damping properties. They have emerged as one of the most promising materials for the 21st century, with potential use in sectors like automobiles, aircraft, aerospace, and the electronic industry [8–10]. However, producing complex structural components from these alloys can be challenging due to their poor ductility and cold processability at room temperature, attributed to their hexagonal close-packed (HCP) crystal structure, resulting in insufficient slip systems [9, 11]. This dilemma is further complicated by the difficulty in managing stable and continuous welding processes due to the physical properties of magnesium, such as its low density, low melting, and boiling point [12, 13]. Since the use of WADED for magnesium alloys is still in its early stages, the suitability

of Cold Metal Transfer (CMT) as a heat source in this process remains an active topic of investigation [5, 14–19]. Multiple studies have highlighted the critical influence of current control on weld quality, identifying key challenges such as premature solidification, unstable droplet detachment, spray transfer phenomena occurring under specific current conditions, and excessive heat input leading to localised overheating [20–22].

This study explores CMT's suitability in WADED of AZ61 magnesium alloy. Its focus is to investigate the CMT process's arc characteristics in order to optimise the weld deposit's contact angle and achieve consistent weld depth throughout the contact area. Identifying key parameters that influence the welding process and explaining their effect on the behaviour of weld deposits is essential for optimizing suitable parameters for the reliable production of AZ61 alloy.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A single-weld deposit test was conducted to evaluate the influence of key parameters on the weld. The arc current and voltage were monitored during the experiment, and the contact angle and weld depth were optimized. Based on the results, suitable parameters were selected, and a thin-walled part was produced and analysed both mechanically and materially.

2.1. Process parameters

The welding was conducted on the base metal (BM) with dimensions of 100 mm × 20 mm × 8 mm from AZ91D magnesium alloy. The AZ61 wire, with a diameter of 1.6 mm, was used as a filler material with a chemical composition provided by the distributor, as listed in Table 1. Weld beads were made using a Fronius TPS 3200 CMT welding system. The positioning movement of the welding torch was accomplished using a KUKA KR 60 HA robotic arm.

Table 1 Chemical composition of AZ61 magnesium alloy wire

Elements	Al	Zn	Mn	Si	Fe	Cu	Ni
Min%	5.50	0.5	0.15				
Max%	6.50	1.50	0.40	0.10	0.005	0.05	0.005

During the tests, a constant speed of the welding torch (WS) of 10 mm/s and a distance from the manufactured part of 13 mm was maintained. Pure argon (99.5 %) was adopted as the shielding gas with a flow rate of 18 l/min. A DC-CMT characteristic given by the synergic line (G3Si1), according to Wang et al. [17], with modifications based on previous experiments was used as a mean value throughout the whole experiment.

Fig. 1 CMT characteristic welding process (Modified [23])

The single-weld deposit experiment consisted of 21 combinations listed in Table 2 created by altering different parameters of the CMT characteristic. The characteristic is shown in Fig. 1 and consists of the 3 main phases: melting of the wire while the movement of the electrode goes upwards (boost phase), returning of the wire back to the weld pool (burn phase) and the contact and transfer of the melted droplet (SC phase).

Table 2 The different settings of CMT characteristic used in experiment

Weld	I_boost (A)	t_I_boost (ms)	I_sc_wait (A)	vd_sc_vait (m·min ⁻¹)	i_sc2 (A)
1	360	2	35	30	40
2	400	2	35	30	40
3	430	2	35	30	40
4	450	2	35	30	40
5	480	2	35	30	40
6	430	1.7	35	30	40
7	430	2.3	35	30	40
8	430	2.6	35	30	40
9	430	3	35	30	40
10	430	2	15	30	40
11	430	2	55	30	40
12	430	2	75	30	40
13	430	2	100	30	40
14	430	2	35	10	40
15	430	2	35	20	40
16	430	2	35	45	40
17	430	2	35	60	40
18	430	2	35	30	20
19	430	2	35	30	60
20	430	2	35	30	80
21	430	2	35	30	100

Five main characteristic parameters can be controlled during the CMT welding process. I_boost (A) - boost phase current, t_I_boost (ms) – boost phase duration, I_sc_wait (A) – burn phase current, vd_sc_wait (m·min⁻¹) – the speed of electrode during the boost and burn phase and I_sc2 (A) – SC phase current. The RCU 5000i controller was used to alter the synergic line and CMT parameters. Fig. 2 shows a schematic diagram of the experimental setup for recording the characteristic waveform. The voltage and current signal were recorded with a Tektronix DPO 2024B using the frequency of 312.5 kHz.

Fig. 2 Schematic of the experimental set-up of CMT welding process

Individual phases of the CMT cycle were measured based on diagram given in Fig. 1. The average power of the cycle was calculated by the value of voltage ($U_{(x)}$) and current ($I_{(x)}$) in every step (n) by Eq. 1:

$$P_c = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{x=0}^n U_{(x)} \cdot I_{(x)} \quad (1)$$

2.2. Geometry analysis, dimensions of samples

Overall, 21 samples were fabricated and analysed, individual samples were cut, and their cross-sections were polished using a series of 3 grinding discs with grit sizes: P320, P500, and P1000. Subsequently, they were polished with a P3000 paste, and the geometry and macrostructure of the weld were observed using an Olympus SZX7 microscope. A diagram of the main dimensions of the weld bead is shown in Fig. 3. Awp represents the area of weld penetration (below the width line). Awr indicates the area of weld reinforcement (above the line).

Fig. 3 Schematic of geometry of weld bead

Based on the findings obtained from the comprehensive parametric study, a set of optimized parameters suitable for Wire Arc Directed Energy Deposition (WADED) was determined. The schematic diagram of the CMT-WADED process is depicted in Fig. 4. The component dimensions were designed to allow the extraction of tensile specimens according to DIN 50125. The start and end points of the trajectories were positioned outside the regions designated for specimen machining to avoid local inhomogeneities in the tensile samples. Using this methodology, a thin-walled component consisting of 50 layers with dimensions of 130 mm x 30 mm x 130 mm was successfully fabricated.

Fig. 4 The schematic diagram of the planned tool paths for production of the thin-walled component

2.3. Material properties and microstructure

Material properties were investigated to describe the achieved microstructure (defects, material phases, grain size) and clarify the material's mechanical behaviour.

Thermodynamic calculations in the Equilibrium state and using the Scheil model were performed using Thermo-Calc software (Version 2024a) and database TCMG6 (Thermo-Calc Software AB, Solna, Sweden). The calculation was carried out using the average chemical composition in Table 1.

Microstructural investigations were done by means of optical light microscopy (OLM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) on polished and polished + etched (picric acid) samples. For OLM, an optical microscope OLYMPUS BX53M with a digital camera OLYMPUS SC180 was used, and the microstructural images were taken by the software OLYMPUS Stream Motion 2.5. A Tescan MIRA 3 scanning electron microscope (TESCAN, Brno, Czech Republic) equipped with a field emission gun (FEG) operated at 15 kV was used for SEM analysis. The electron images were taken using a four-quadrant backscattered electron detector (TESCAN, Brno, Czech Republic) operated at a working distance of 15 mm. The element analysis (EDS) was performed using an EDAX (Mahwah, NJ, USA) Octane Elect silicon drift detector system. The fracture surfaces of tensile specimens were examined by digital-light microscope (Keyence VHX-6000, Z250R lens, magnification 250).

2.4. Mechanical testing

The samples for microstructural investigation and tensile tests were extracted from the thin-walled part in the way you can see in picture Fig. 5. The tensile specimens had dimensions according to DIN 50125, test piece type E, and test piece thickness of 3 mm. Tensile tests were conducted at room temperature using a universal testing machine (Shimadzu AGX-V 100kN, Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan). The deformation rate during testing was $0.5 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$.

Fig. 5 Schematic position of specimen extraction (a) specimens in transversal direction (TD) and (b) welding direction (WD)

A 2-camera 3D DIC (digital image correlation) system from Dantec Dynamics (Skovlunde, Denmark) was used to measure the ductility of the samples. The system hardware consisted of two 5 MPx cameras (2448×2048 px resolution, $3.45 \mu\text{m}$ pixel size) with 50 mm lenses. The baseline was set to 160 mm, resulting in a 17-degree stereo angle suitable for planar samples. The frame rate was set at 0.5 Hz. The correlation parameters were adjusted for better reliability – 29-pixel facet size with 19 px spacing.

The in-plane anisotropy percentage (%IPA) can be calculated to assess the degree of anisotropy in the tensile properties. The %IPA(X), where X represents the tensile property index, was calculated by the maximum value obtained from the building and travel directions (X_{max}) and the minimum value from the building and travel directions (X_{min}) by Eq. 2 [24]:

$$\%IPA(X) = \frac{X_{max} - X_{min}}{X_{max}} \quad (2)$$

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Effect of CMT characteristic

Boost phase current (I_{boost})

Increasing the current from 360 A to 480 A in the welding process led to noteworthy changes in heat input, bead geometry, and cycle times. Initially, at 360 A, the heat input (P_c) was 1356.1 W, but it rose significantly to 2004.9 W at 400 A and further to 2396.7 W at the peak current of 480 A, see in Fig. 6 (a). Concurrently, the cycle time (T_c) was the longest (16.9 ms) at 360 A and then decreased sharply to 13.2 ms. With the further increase in current, the cycle times showed minor fluctuation.

Fig. 6 Influence of characteristic parameters on energy input of CMT welding process: (a) I_{boost} , (b) $t_{I_{boost}}$, (c) I_{sv_wait} , (d) vd_{sc_wait} , (e) I_{sc2}

The sudden drop in cycle time observed between 360 A and 400 A is atypical. As demonstrated in He's study [20], an increase in current typically leads to an increase in droplet size. Given that the droplet diameter exceeds the wire diameter, the duration of the burn phase would be expected to increase accordingly. However, as shown by [21], an increase in droplet size does not necessarily result in a longer burn time; instead, the burn phase duration remains relatively consistent despite the rising boost current. A similar trend was observed in this study in Fig. 6 (a) while increasing the boost current from 400 A to 480 A.

Regarding bead geometry Fig. 7 (a) and Fig. 8 (a), an increase in current led to the weld bead's width expansion from 6.3 mm to 9.6 mm and a decrease in its height from 3.9 mm to 2.8 mm. This change is attributed to the variable surface tension and a smaller weld pool size, leading to a greater spread of the droplet on contact with the weld pool [21]. The increase in current also resulted in an increased weld penetration depth from 0.34 mm to 0.51 mm.

Fig. 7 Influence of parameters on weld geometry: (y) I_{boost} , (b) $t_{I_{boost}}$, (c) I_{sc_wait} , (d) vd_{sc_wait} , (e) I_{sc2}

The weld bead area (A_{wp}) showed some fluctuations. It increased from 0.53 mm^2 (at 360 A) to 1.26 mm^2 (at 400 A), followed by a minor reduction to 0.9 mm^2 (at 430 A) and a final increase to 1.6 mm^2 (at 480 A). The largest weld bead area of 22.9 mm^2 was achieved at 430 A with a wire feed speed (WFS) of $6.1 \text{ m} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$. However, the weld bead area decreased slightly for currents of 450 A and 480 A. This was likely due to overheating leading to vaporization, causing the molten droplet to deflect and prematurely detach, falling outside the weld pool [11, 25].

Boost phase duration ($t_{I_{boost}}$)

As the boost time increased, the average power also rose, reaching a peak of 2450 W at 3 ms. The total cycle time exhibited a convex trend, with a minimum duration of 13.2 ms observed at a boost time of 2.3 ms. The correlation of the trend in burn and short-circuit phases can be seen in the graph Fig. 6 (a) of the I_{boost} parameter. In contrast, in the graph Fig. 6 (b), increasing the $t_{I_{boost}}$ did not lead to a similar obvious correlation between the mentioned parameters.

Fig. 8 Influence of characteristic parameters on weld geometry: (a) I_{boost} , (b) $t_{I_{boost}}$, (c) vd_{sc_wait} , (e) I_{sc2} , Awp – weld penetration area, Awr – weld reinforcement area

In weld bead geometry Fig. 7 (b) and Fig. 8 (b), increasing the boost phase current led to an increase in the bead's width (from 6.3 mm to 9.6 mm) and a decrease in its height (from 3.9 mm to 2.8 mm). This resulted in a higher contact angle from 68° to 110° and an increased weld penetration depth from 0.34 mm to 0.51 mm.

Increased boost phase duration expanded the weld bead area. It led to a decrease in bead height for width, similar to the I_{boost} parameter. An exception was noticed at a boost phase duration of 3 ms, where a significant increase in both the bead's height and area occurred. Simultaneously, a reduced cycle length followed the same pattern as Fig. 6 (a). This reduction was due to an extended burn phase at a boost phase duration of 1.7 ms, likely because the boost phase ended before the electrode's oscillatory movement [21]. The overall cycle length increased for boost phase durations of 2.6 ms and 3 ms due to the larger droplet size.

Burn phase current ($I_{\text{sc_wait}}$)

The highest average cycle work of 2228.5 W was measured at a current of 15 A. Changes in this parameter showed a strong correlation with the current magnitude, akin to the I_{boost} and $t_{\text{I_boost}}$ parameters, with exceptions observed at 75 A and 100 A due to increased cycle durations reaching 24.8 ms and 24.6 ms, respectively. These duration changes led to corresponding increases in both the burn and SC phases, as illustrated in Fig. 6 (c).

The increase in the overall cycle time and the duration of each individual phase can be attributed to the interaction of two factors. During the boost phase, the droplet is melted, and upon transition to the burn phase, the continued current input supports further droplet growth. Simultaneously, the magnitude of the burn phase current induces a recoil effect, leading to droplet flattening and consequently prolonging the burn phase. When the droplet eventually contacts the weld pool, the electrode position is lower, and its subsequent emergence from the solidifying weld pool takes longer, thereby extending the SC phase. A similar recoil behaviour was observed in Gomez's study [22].

Only slight increases in height, width, and contact angle with the $I_{\text{sc_wait}}$ parameter were seen, unlike the significant changes in the other parameters. However, weld penetration depth did increase from 0.27 mm at 15 A to 0.59 mm at 100 A, as per Fig. 7 (c) and Fig. 8 (c). The wire feed speed remained constant at $6 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ for 35 A and 75 A.

The I_{boost} and $t_{\text{I_boost}}$ parameters consistently showed an increase in droplet size when reducing the overall cycle length. The $I_{\text{sc_wait}}$ parameter, which controls the burn phase current, demonstrated a continuous increase in cycle length and corresponding increases in the burn and SC phase lengths. This led to a slight increase in droplet size but not as pronounced changes in weld bead geometry as seen with the other parameters, resulting in smaller variations in phase durations.

A likely explanation is the interaction of two processes. In the boost phase, a droplet forms and grows when transitioning into the burn phase due to increased burn phase current. However, the current magnitude introduces a slight backlash that flattens the droplet, extending the burn phase cycle.

Electrode speed during the boost and burn phase ($vd_{\text{sc_wait}}$)

The study found the average cycle work mirrored the pattern of cycle length, peaking (2065 W) at the minimum cycle length of 13.6 ms and hitting a low (1404 W) at the maximum cycle length of 23.7 ms. Similar to the $I_{\text{sc_wait}}$ parameter, the $vd_{\text{sc_wait}}$ parameter did not cause significant changes in weld geometry. However, weld height and contact angle varied with speed, and penetration depth dramatically dropped from 0.41 mm at $30 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ to 0.11 mm at 45 and $60 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. This corresponded to a decrease in weld area and weld bead area.

Fig. 9 Comparison of CMT characteristic: (a) Mean value, (b) vd_{sc_wait} ($10 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$)

Notably, an unstable characteristic profile Fig. 9 (b) occurred at a $10 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ electrode speed in the burn phase, which exhibited a significantly longer burn phase duration relative to the SC phase durations. Previous work observed a substantial increase in droplet size and burn phase duration in aluminium alloy welding at $5 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. This increased surface tension and a weld bead geometry composed of multiple continuous spot welds [21, 22].

Analyzing characteristics in Fig. 6 (d), burn phase duration decreased with speed until $30 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, after which it stabilized. Conversely, the SC phase duration increased with speed due to smaller droplet formation and deeper electrode submergence into the weld pool. A cycle length increases at $10 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, $20 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, $45 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, and $60 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ was accompanied by a decrease in cycle work. Finally, comparing maximum cycle work with weld penetration size showed the highest penetration at a speed of $30 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, with penetration decreasing at speeds of $45 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and $60 \text{ m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$.

SC phase current (I_{sc2})

The maximum average cycle work Fig. 6 (e), (2065 W) corresponded with the shortest cycle length (13.6 ms), and the minimum average cycle work (1627.2 W) with the most extended cycle length (18.4 ms). This correlation was reflected in the lengths of the burn and SC phases. When the current magnitude of the SC phase was changed Fig. 7 (e) and Fig. 8 (e), weld height stayed constant (3.6 - 3.8 mm). Weld penetration depth increased from 0.38 mm at 20 A to 0.72 mm at 100 A. The contact angle stayed stable between 101° and 104° . The weld area increased noticeably, from 0.65 mm^2 at 20 A to 2 mm^2 . Likewise, the weld bead size increased from 21.6 mm^2 to 25.2 mm^2 at 80 A, with a slight decrease to 24.9 mm^2 .

The I_{sc2} parameter controls the current magnitude from when the transferred droplet touches the weld pool until the electrode detaches from the pool. Despite the voltage always reaching minimum (non-zero) values in this phase, an increase in SC phase current led to increased weld penetration. This increase, however, caused subtle changes in weld height and width.

3.2. Evaluation of parametrical study and WADED

The combination (based on previous findings) of parameters listed in Table 3 was selected to optimize both the weld geometry and penetration depth while ensuring the stability of the process. These parameter settings were explicitly chosen to minimize material loss, achieve the desired contact angle range of 90-120°, and prevent significant growth in weld geometry.

Table 3 Table of CMT parameters used for WADED

I_boost	t_I_boost	I_sc_wait	vd_sc_wait	I_sc2
(A)	(ms)	(A)	(m·min-1)	(A)
430	2.5	35	30	50

The optimized parameters were implemented, resulting in a stable welding process that achieved a contact angle of 108° and a consistent weld depth throughout the contact area. Wire Arc Directed Energy Deposition (WADED) benefited from the application of these parameters, leading to significant improvements in penetration depth, which was evenly distributed across the entire width of the weld Fig. 10. The successful weld exhibited a suitable contact angle of 108°, making it well-suited for thin-walled parts. The final part of Fig. 11 dimensions were 130x60x130 mm, with a wall width of 9.8 mm, indicating successful prevention of excessive overheating.

Fig. 10 Weld deposited with parameters used for WADED

However, it is essential to acknowledge that the production process encountered challenges. The presence of impurities in the wire and deviations in the welding trajectory introduced errors during manufacturing. Despite these obstacles, implementing the optimized parameters proved highly effective in achieving the desired weld characteristics.

Fig. 11 AZ61 thin-walled object fabricated by WADED

3.3. Material analysis

Phase fraction calculations for the AZ61 alloy based on the average composition in Table 1 are illustrated in Fig. 12, with (a) representing the equilibrium state and (b) using the Scheil equation. The elements Fe, Cu, and Ni were omitted from the calculations because, although they are common impurities, their content is low.

The calculations indicate that the intermetallic β -phase $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ forms in significant quantities in addition to the Mg solid solution. This phase precipitates directly from the solid solution at temperatures below 300 °C according to the equilibrium calculation. However, at conventional (non-equilibrium) solidification in technical processes, this phase often precipitates primarily from the melt, forming a divorced eutectic β -phase at the grain boundaries [13]. This is supported by the Scheil calculation, where the $Mg_{17}Al_{12}$ phase forms at temperatures around 425 °C and, therefore, above the solidus temperature.

Furthermore, the calculations show that Al-Mn phases are formed primarily, with variable stoichiometries (Al_8Mn_5 , $Al_{11}Mn_4$ and Al_4Mn). It is known from practice that mainly Al_8Mn_5 is formed, which is stable down to room temperature [26]. With silicon, which typically exists as an impurity in technical Mg-Al alloys, the intermetallic phase Mg_2Si can form. According to the calculations in Fig. 12, this phase forms primarily from the melt.

The equilibrium calculation also shows the formation of an $AlMgZn$ phase, which precipitates from the solid solution at temperatures below 100 °C. However, this phase does not typically form during conventional processing conditions due to the very low diffusion rate at these temperatures.

Fig. 12 : Equilibrium (a) and Scheil (b) phase calculations for magnesium AZ61 using the average composition given in Table 1 (Fe, Cu, Ni omitted).

The longitudinal section of the Mg AZ61 wire, captured using light microscopy, is depicted in Fig. 13. The wire is partially significantly oxidized, with oxides particularly prevalent on the wire surface, decreasing towards the centre. A possible cause could be improper storage of the sensitive Mg wire before processing. Furthermore, band-like arranged blocky Al-Mn phases with a maximum size of 30 μm can be observed, especially in the wire centre. It is assumed that these are primarily formed Al_8Mn_5 phases from the casting process, which align along the deformation direction during wire manufacturing. In addition to the larger Al-Mn particles in the wire centre, the same phases can be found finely distributed throughout the wire.

Fig. 13 Longitudinal section of the used Mg AZ61 wire

Figure Fig. 14 shows the microstructure of a WADED sample. The oxides clearly present in the wires (see Fig. 13) are significantly smaller and homogeneously distributed in the WADED sample. Distributed blocky Al-Mn phases can be found throughout the WADED sample. Due to the high cooling rate in the WADED process, their size is somewhat smaller, with a maximum of 20 μm , than those in the wire. Additionally, Mg-Al phases can be observed at the grain boundaries. It is assumed and supported by the calculations that these are β -phases ($\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}$), which appear as divorced eutectic. The β -phase content is low throughout the sample, so a continuous network does not form, but rather, the phase appears as individual islands. Sporadically, globular-shaped pores with sizes of up to 70 μm and localized shrinkage voids are discernible.

Fig. 14 Microstructure of a WADED sample

The microstructure of an etched WADED sample observed under polarized light is illustrated in Fig. 15. Due to the different grain sizes, the intralayer zone and fusion zone are clearly distinguishable. At the location where a new layer is applied to an already existing layer (fusion zone), the cooling rate is higher, resulting in a fine microstructure in the lower part of the new layer. Farther away from the underlying layer, the solidification rate is lower, resulting in an increased grain size. Similar microstructures were observed for Al alloys processed via WADED by Klein et al. [27]. Graf et al. have found that the zones in WADED AZ91 can also be distinguished by the different proportions of β -phase [28]. However, this was not investigated in this work. Based on the micrograph, the layer height is approximately ~ 1.5 mm.

Fig. 15 Microstructure of an etched WADED sample observed under polarized light

3.4. Mechanical properties

Three samples oriented in the welding direction (WD) and three in the transversal direction (TD) were tested to obtain the mechanical properties of the AZ61 thin-walled object. The ultimate tensile strength (UTS), yield strength (YS), and elongation (A) were calculated from the stress-strain curves, and the results are listed in Table 4. Fig. 16 shows the stress strain curves of tensile specimens.

Fig. 16 Tensile results of WADED thin-walled object – WD (welding direction), TD (transversal direction)

The results show that the average yield strength in the WD direction is 114.78 MPa, in the TD direction 110.42 MPa, and a %IPA(YS) anisotropy is 0.139. The average tensile strengths of the material are 239.15 MPa in the WD direction and 173.34 MPa in the TD direction, thus differing more significantly, and the %IPA(UTS) is 0.438. The greatest anisotropy is shown by the elongation %IPA(A) of 0.874, with average elongation values in the WD direction of 7.96% and the TD direction of 4.16%. Ultimate tensile strength in the TD direction is close to the values achieved in castings. Yield strength in both directions and ultimate tensile strength in the welding direction are higher than comparable casted magnesium alloys but lower than for AZ61 forgings.

Table 4 Mechanical properties of AZ61 thin-walled object

Direction	Ultimate tensile strength UTS (MPa)	Yield strength YS (MPa)	Elongation A (%)
Welding direction (WD)	239.15 ± 7.41	114.78 ± 5.42	7.96 ± 1.79
Transversal direction (TD)	173.34 ± 31.79	110.42 ± 6.14	4.16 ± 2.55

The measured values indicate that the UTS and A of samples made from a thin-walled object exhibit significant anisotropy between the WD and TD directions. However, the overall anisotropy values can be partially distorted by significant differences between the behaviour of the samples in the TD direction.

Sample TD_3 shows significantly worse UTS and A values than the other samples in the TD direction. It can be caused, for example, by local defects in the sample. From the fractographic images of the fracture surfaces, as seen in Fig. 17 (a), it is evident that sample TD_3 contains noticeable large local pores both inside the sample and at its edge. Such porous and heterogeneous texture of fracture surface was observed only in sample TD_3. The other samples showed a homogeneous, smooth fracture surface without significant protrusions, similar to sample WD_1, see Fig. 17 (b). Such a defect at the edge of the sample TD_3 can become a stress concentrator and an initiator of crack growth in the material. This local defect would explain the deviation of the UTS and A values of sample TD_3 from the other samples in the TD direction.

Fig. 17 Fracture surfaces after tensile testing (a) left two pictures TD_3, (b) right two pictures WD_1

However, even if deviated sample TD3 were not considered, the material would still show observable anisotropy in the TD and WD directions. The anisotropy calculated without this sample reaches approximately half the values. The anisotropy values without TD_3 are: %IPA(YS) is 0.139; %IPA(UTS) is 0.227, and %IPA(A) is 0.441. Even such anisotropy values are not satisfactory, but they are not unique. Several authors involved in WAAM production observed a similarly large anisotropy. Yang et al. [14] observed similar anisotropy values directly on the magnesium alloy AZ31. Yang et al. identified epitaxial columnar dendritic growth along the transversal direction as the leading cause of the anisotropy, whereas mechanical properties showed worse properties in the welding direction. In this work, the mechanical properties showed worse properties in the transverse direction, so another phenomenon probably causes the anisotropy.

Other common causes of anisotropy include the alternation of fusion zone and interlayer zone associated with applying material layer by layer. A more detailed description of why layers with different grain sizes were observed in the transverse direction is in Chapter 3.3. The anisotropy caused by different grain sizes across the transverse direction is described by Kumar et al. [29], who confirmed the connection between grain size and mechanical properties in WAAM samples according to the Hall-

Petch relationship. Smaller grains act as barriers to dislocation motion, increasing strength. In areas with larger grains, dislocation occurs more easily, and mechanical properties deteriorate.

Another possible cause of anisotropy described by Kumar et al. [29] is the effect of residual stresses. A sizeable thermal gradient occurs during manufacturing due to rapid heating and cooling cycles. These thermal cycles induce residual stresses due to uneven contraction of the deposited material.

3.5. Challenges and future work

This article is an initial study on developing suitable parameters for producing thin-walled parts from magnesium alloy AZ61. The influence of process parameters on the appearance of weld deposits was observed. The produced thin-walled part was tested, and key points influencing the production process were identified. Based on these findings, the production process will be improved to achieve a reliable production process. The quality of the feeding wire is essential from the point of view of process stability and elimination of local defects. Impurities of any kind in the filler wire are also the cause of unwanted porosity [16]. It is necessary to store the wire correctly to prevent oxidation and clean it before production. For this reason, great emphasis will be placed on quality control of the input wire in subsequent experiments. It is also essential to ensure control of interpass temperatures and maintain the same conditions throughout the entire production. Guaranteeing the same conditions in the whole production process should eliminate areas where the welding process is unstable, and thus, defects and inhomogeneity occur. Ensuring homogeneous process conditions and applying appropriate heat treatment after production can significantly reduce or completely eliminate anisotropy. Heat treatment reduces residual stresses and homogenizes grain size in the whole part, positively affecting mechanical properties. Guo et al. [30] demonstrated that heat treatment enhanced mechanical properties in AZ80M fabricated using WADED and concluded that an appropriate heat treatment strategy can effectively eliminate anisotropy. Therefore, in follow-up studies, attention will be focused on process parameters and postprocessing, such as heat treatment or corrosion protection, which is also an important topic.

Compared to other additive technologies such as Laser Powder Bed Fusion (L-PBF) or Electron Beam Powder Bed Fusion (EB-PBF), WADED has several advantages, including production efficiency, acquisition cost, input material cost and the possibility of producing large-sized parts [31]. Disadvantages include poorer dimensional accuracy, less complexity of the shapes fabricated and poorer surface quality. Mechanical properties of AZ61 alloy produced by L-PBF technology with appropriate heat treatment reach UTS 240 MPa, YS 124 MPa and EL 5.9% [32]. These values are comparable to those achieved by WADED technology if proper heat treatment is applied. The mechanical properties of AZ61 alloy or similar ones produced by conventional technologies are as follows. Forgings of AZ61 alloy reach UTS 295 MPa, YS 180 MPa and EL 12% [13]. Castings are not usually made from AZ61 alloy; the most similar casting alloys are AZ63 and AZ91. The AZ63 sand-cast alloy achieves UTS of 200 MPa, YS of 97 MPa and EL of 6%, and the AZ91 sand-cast alloy achieves UTS of 165 MPa, YS of 97 MPa and EL of 2.5% [13]. The mechanical properties reported in this paper are higher than those for castings, lower than forgings, and approximately comparable to those produced by L-PBF. After eliminating the aforementioned problematic issues and achieving a reliable manufacturing process chain, WADED technology, in combination with magnesium alloys, can have a significant industrial impact. Since optimized parts for the transportation industry often contain thin-walled parts, it is essential to further develop the manufacturing process, including postprocessing.

CONCLUSION

This paper is focused on developing suitable parameters for producing thin-walled parts from magnesium alloy, identifying the impact of main process parameters on weld deposit. Magnesium alloy wire AZ61 was deposited on base plates by the CMT welding process using various characteristic parameters. The primary conclusions from these results are as follows:

- Boost phase current has significantly affected cycle time and droplet surface tension, resulting in wider and lower welds. Change in Boost duration resulted in rapid material consumption growth, resulting in a bigger weld area.
- Electrode speed during the boost and burn phase significantly impacted the stability of the welding process and welded depth. SC phase current directly correlates to weld depth and has a minor effect on the weld bead's width, height and contact angle.
- Through optimization of specific welding parameters, a stable welding process was achieved, leading to notable improvements in penetration depth, contact angle, and consistent weld depth, suitable for Wire Arc Directed Energy Deposition (WADED).
- The tensile properties show apparent anisotropic behaviour due to the different grain sizes in interlayer and fusion zones. The average UTS, YS, and A of the welding direction specimens are distinctly superior to those of the transversal direction specimens. The anisotropy of the UTS, YS, and EL for the AZ61 deposit are 0.438, 0.139 and 0.874. Mitigating anisotropy in future applications will require filler wire quality improvement, precise control of thermal conditions during deposition, and implementation of suitable heat treatment strategies.
- Ultimate tensile strength in the TD direction of 173.34 MPa is close to the values achieved in castings. Yield strength in both directions, YS(TD) 110.42 MPa, YS(WD) 114.78 MPa and ultimate tensile strength in the welding direction 239.15 MPa, are higher than those for castings, lower than forgings, and approximately comparable to those produced by L-PBF.

In conclusion, adjusting CMT characteristic parameters can control the heat input and transfer process, thus resulting in the capability to optimize the welding process for WADED application.

Funding

This article presents research results that have received funding from the specific research project of faculty FSI-S-23-8340 and from project MEBioSYS - "Mechanical Engineering of Biological and Bio-inspired Systems", funded as project no. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004634 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo Repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15055769>.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT and Grammarly in order to improve language and readability. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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